

ISic1058

I.Sicily inscription 1058

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2015.01.17

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Quarry of the Intagliatella

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Archeologico
Gabriele Judica, inventory 2269

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140538

1. ἐνθ[ά]δε κῆτε Μαρκιανή
2. □ σεμνή [κ](αὶ) ἄμεμπτος βιώσ [ασα]
3. ἰς τὸν κόσμον τοῦτον· ἄπε #⁷ -
4. χώρι ²⁶ἀπεχώρι²⁶ πρὸς [τ](ὸν) [Κ]ύριον ἐτῶν
5. α □ ω ι#⁵⁶α', [ψυ]χὴν π[ρολιπ]οῦσα τῆ
6. πρὸ θ καλ (ανδῶν) Ἰανουαρ-
7. ἰων. τὸν δὲ θεόν σε, φίλε,
8. μή μου σκύλης τὸν βόθ-
9. ρον, μή μοι δίξης φῶς·
10. ἄ[ν]] δὲ θελήσης φοῦς ²⁶φῶς²⁶ μοι
11. δίξε, σοὶ τὸ φῶς
12. ὁ θ (εὐ) ς ΧΟΛΙ[.]ΟΝ ²⁷χόλιον?²⁷ δώση.
13. □ ἰχθύς ²⁶Ι(ησοῦς) Χ(ριστὸς) θ(εοῦ) υ(ἰὸς) σ(ωτήρ)²⁶.
14. ²palmula²
- 15.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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